

LIPIDS OF THE AERIAL PARTS OF ARTEMISIA ANNUA L.

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17341469>

Relevance: Lipids of medicinal plants are of interest as a source of biologically active compounds. *Artemisia annua* L. (annual wormwood) is known for its antimalarial and anti-inflammatory properties, but the lipid composition of its aboveground parts has not been sufficiently studied.

The aim of the study: To determine the content, composition and fatty acid profile of neutral and polar lipids of the aboveground part of *Artemisia annua* L.

Materials and methods: Air-dried above-ground part of *Artemisia annua* L. Neutral lipids were isolated by extraction with gasoline (b.p. 75–80 °C). Polar lipids were extracted using the Folch method with a mixture of chloroform and methanol (2:1 v/v) and purified with a 0.04% CaCl 2 solution . The component composition was determined by TLC. The fatty acid composition was determined by gas chromatography (Agilent 6890N).

Results: Lipid content is shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Lipid characteristics of the aboveground part *Artemisia annua* L .

Indicator	Content
1. Moisture, % of the weight of the above-ground part	8.6
2. Total lipids, % of the weight of the aboveground part, including:	5.89
2a. Neutral lipids, %	4.34
2b. Polar lipids, %	1.55
3. Content, mg/l: chlorophyll " a "	1.5
chlorophyll " b "	0.5

Component composition: NL contain hydrocarbons, fatty acid esters with phytosterols and triterpenols , triacylglycerides , free fatty acids and alcohols, triterpenols , phytosterols , chlorophyll pigments.

PL are represented by glycolipids and phospholipids.

The fatty acid composition according to (GC) is given in Table 2

Table 2. Fatty acid composition of the aboveground part of *Artemisia annua* L. GC, % of the mass of acids

No.	Fatty acid	Samples	
		NL	PL
1	Linoleic , 18 :2	41,2	35.1
2	Oleic, 18 : 1	20.5	10.5
3	α - Linolenic, 18 : 3	7.9	5.7
4	Palmitic, 16:00	18.4	14.9

5	Linolenic, 18 : 3	1.7	24.9
6	Stearic, 18:0	3.5	2.2
7	Myristic , 14:0	2.2	1.5
8	Arachinovaya , 20:00	1.5	1.7
9	Eicosene , 20:1	1.8	1.0
10	Begenova , 22:00	1.3	1.9
	Σ saturated fatty acids	26.9	22.2
	Σ unsaturated fatty acids	73.1	77.2

Conclusions : • Lipids of the aboveground part of *Artemisia annua* L. are rich in unsaturated fatty acids (73.1% in NL, 77.2% in PL).

- Essential acids: linoleic , oleic, linolenic, palmitic.
- The data obtained expand the knowledge about the chemical composition of *Artemisia annua* and can be used to develop pr preparations and functional products.